

Table 1. – Questionnaire Applied to the Interviews for “Enablers and Challenges that Influence the Agile Transformation Journey”, a Paper Research

Part / Focus	Questions
Part I - Planning the adoption of agile alternatives	(Q1) In a macro way, how is (or was) the process of transition to the current state of the organization when adopting agile practices? (Q2) Was there an assessment of the current status of the process? How was it done? (Q3) How was the decision to adopt the practices communicated? What was the perceived impact on the organizational climate in the face of this challenge? (Q4) Why did your team/organization adopt agile practices? (Q5) What could facilitate organizational engagement?
Part II – Implementing the adoption of agile alternatives	(Q6) Were the technical disciplines (requirements, analysis, and projects, tests, codification, and implementation) prepared for the adoption of agile practices? What were the adjustments? (Q7) How was the adaptation of traditional management roles, more specifically Functional IT Management, Human Resources, and PMO - Project Management Office? (Q8) What best agility practices have been adopted, or are in adoption? And why were these practices selected? (Q9) Is your organization structured by projects or products? Is the value stream of the products defined and managed end-to-end? How is that done currently? Do you think the current structure is adequate, and what are the plans for the future? (Q10) What could facilitate the adaptation of processes, practices, structures, and culture for agility adoption?
Part III - Issues in the Agile Adoption Journey	(Q11) What were the main challenges/problems? (Q12) In terms of organizational structure, cite 3 points that helped the most and 3 that became impediments or challenges to be overcome. (Q13) How was the process of training those involved? Did you find it satisfactory? What would you recommend differently? (Q14) What could have mitigated or avoided some problems and challenges?
Part IV - Best practices of continuous improvement during the agile transition	(Q15) Does the process being adopted (or which was adopted) have a measurement mechanism to capture what worked and what needs to improve in the process (not in the product)? Are there scheduled cycles? Is there a backlog of changes, risks, and improvements? (Q16) Do you think that the values and principles of agility are known and followed by the team? (Q17) What factors identified in monitoring served to accelerate the process of agility adoption? (Q18) What could have been done to accelerate/enable adoption?
Part V – Technical areas and ITSM	(Q19) In a macro way, what is the technological/digital scenario of your organization? Does this scenario influence (or not) the adoption process? How? (Q20) Were the technical areas such as architecture, quality, data, and others involved in the transition process? What actions were taken for these areas to converge their results to the expected agility results? (Q21) In architectural terms, is your organization prepared for digital transformation? With low coupling design and distributed architectures such as containers? (P22) What is the level of automation in testing, CI / CD, infrastructure, and support? (Q23) Do you believe that any architectural/technical adjustment could have been applied in your organization to potentiate the success of agile adoption initiatives?
Part VI – Future Planning	(Q24) What are the next steps in adopting agility? (Q25) What are the new challenges, in your view?